

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL BASIS OF RAISING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN GENERAL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: and in this article, the quality of education in the overall education system of monitoring the implementation of collaboration between several pedagogical, psychological and social aspects of collaboration from an integral to a certain extent independent from the establishment of the concept, and the quality of education, monitoring and the concept of the model showing the mentioned in the article.

Keywords: secondary schools, personnel, teachers, developing action strategies, quality of education, pupils.

The quality of education in general education institutions, on a systematic basis and evaluate the factors that influence it: "the education system of the state and society should be the guarantor of continuous development and improvement. They are highly qualified professionals able to compete on the combination of the activities of the educational institutions for the preparation of should" regard the most important tasks stained sign withn.

Quality of education in general education institutions by the condition of its productive tools for monitoring the elections, taking advantage of opportunities of information and communication technology at a reasonable price, timely korreksiyalanib of the factors that have negative effects on the quality of education, future-oriented measures are enhanced, international compliance requirements in relation to the training of the quality of education it provides.

Assessment of education quality monitoring, indicators in today's day to go to the continuous improvement of the members listed one of the most important priorities, and to ensure the necessary level of quality of education the quality of education in relation to the development of effective methods of management and kvalimetriyasining methodological approach, the main function is in the formation ofdi.

The evaluation of the quality of education is relatively well-known systems of great britain, usa and france are used. A system like this in the uk from 1948 in the usa from 1969, while in france, since 1979, is available. The national system for the evaluation of the quality of education from 1978 to Chilida are being applied in practice. This system allows you to collect all of the necessary information on a regular basis. Pain later than in other countries such systemsis at yd.

In most cis countries to the development of the national system for the evaluation of the quality of education started from 1990.

The purpose of the system of national education within the framework of such appraisal of the recipients of this system is to determine the level of mastering. To do this, the following is necessary:

- determine the degree of master in the field of education;

- possessing the knowledge and skills to identify the strengths and weaknesses of buyers education;

- education mastering identify problems associated with the recipient;
- identify the factors associated with mastering; - maintaining mastering the dynamics.

The system is also being developed at the country level than a variety of district, methodology, methods and other features birbiridan is dramatically different. U.S. national system for the quality assessment of the educational process (NAEP – national assessment of educational progress) the purpose of the reading of children and adolescents, evaluation consists of computing and communication skills. This assessment programs:

- ensure the implementation of the educational program;
- provide feedback to increase the level of mastering;
- provide information for parents;
- umumlashgan get information about the level of development of the educational institution;
- for the formation of national statistics is held.

The purpose of the national assessment system of france the following is from:

- assessment by students of the process of development of science;
- the teacher of measures to assist in the selection;
- to assist teachers in the planning of pedagogical activity [69];

Comprehensive quality control and assessment of the state and by public authorities in great britain is carried out. Today, the assessment of the quality of education bildirilayotgan interest by many countries by each educational institution providing quality education system of the uk establishment and implementation of effective internal monitoring, as well as at the institution of education is characterized by the practice of his engine to be included in the warranty. Thus, the evaluation of the effectiveness of the internal mechanism of quality assurance process is the responsibility of the organization, the complexity of comprehensive quality assurance agency – Agency quality assurance (qa) that are entrusted to undertake. Quality assurance agency (1997) – a non-governmental organization from the organization and its main function is to be held, and the quality of the examination is based on the conclusion of the external examination of the state of the organization will make appropriate decisions on the results of the assessment.

Comprehensive quality control of education academic standards by the agency in support of general education institutions to ensure high academic quality, comprehensive, continuous and systematic improvement of the system and go to the members to ensure compliance and acceptable for all target the main task of general education is defined as. Also, in the evaluation process teachers and education personnel, quality control and special attention to the part of the customer equalsdi.

The quality of education in germany, in particular, a specific evaluation of the quality of general education system. Several agencies in germany currently operates on the assessment of the quality, and some of them narrow range of technical, medical, business sohalarigagina is directed if all of the rest in the other areas of the agency evaluation of education programs, accreditation ixtiscoslashtirilgan. In this state, the process is carried out according to the requirements of the institution akkreditatsiyalash general education shall be formed by the relevant state bodies and the final conclusion. Education in germany independent assessment of the quality of education quality assessment system in which the uniqueness of the system,

be available at the quality of education experts, including full use of the potential of attention to methods in the evaluation ofn.

Also in japan and other developed countries like akkreditatsiyalash assessment of the quality of education the process of self-examination to foreign expertise and deciding if the activities of the educational institution and the commission on the evaluation of special education programs on the basis of overall assessment is carried out. General education assessment of the effectiveness of internal control and quality management of educational institution form the basis of modern methods of analysisidi.

In the republic of science, culture, production, clearly to afford the rapid development in the field of education is removed. In particular, radical reforms in the education system were carried out on 26 September 2012, the cabinet of ministers of the republic of uzbekistan "general education institutions of pedagogical personnel and training measures for further improvement of the system of retraining on"278 dated on the implementation of monitoring education quality "...a systematic analysis of the quality of the education process and its results, the pedagogical skills necessary to ensure comprehensive quality in accordance with the requirements of modern professional monitors and assesses changes in the development of the disabled" to note thatn.

Each year on the teaching of science program in secondary education institutions in the regulations on the quality of the monitoring procedure "...the areas of education and specialties exemplary educational plans and programs in accordance with the requirements of the state educational standard proposals and to develop recommendations on the improvement of the" set

In addition, the prospects of the economy orders to prepare personnel in the area of the formation, qualification requirements, which graduates to put the development of network specialists needed to require participation in the preparation of the process to ensure the quality of the answer does not give you the general education program to ensure that they are in sync with the changing requirements of the labour market systematic work carried out by employers was noted.

The recommendations proposed by the foreign experts group, given the quality of the preparation of specialists with higher education in increasing the participation of the sectors of the economy and the further expansion of the network of the republic through competitive training highly qualified in the content of the general education system ijtimoiyiqtisodiy development prospects of the country, the needs of society, science, culture, technology and technology of modern achievements of the president of the republic of uzbekistan for the purpose of improvement of proceeding from 27 July 2017. "in the preparation of specialists with higher education in increasing the quality of measures for the further expansion of the network, and participation of sectors of the economy"on pp-3151-resolution qawas bul.

This law would and documents:

- secondary institutions of the republic of uzbekistan "on education"the general state of the law and the rules of the established standards, qualification requirements, curricula, and educational sciences, in which the implementation of the monitoring of compliance with the program of sciences;

- the high quality of education and economic and social reforms carried out in the deep country, to the requirements of developed democratic nation-building of personnel preparation;

- education demokratlashuvi, and insonparvarlashuvi ijtimoiylashuv, education and the recipient of the level of legal and economic knowledge, as well as to increase the effectiveness of the education process;

- evaluation criteria and procedures specify the quality of the education and training of the activity;

- education and preparation of personnel to ensure consistent and continuous process of education, bachelor and master maqbullashtirish stages in the educational process;

- the provision of quality educational services, education and training in the field of the person, society and the protection of the interests of the state;

- labor and ensure competitiveness in the market of educational services;

- established comprehensive state education standards, qualification requirements, curricula, and educational sciences and the sciences in which the implementation of the program compliance monitoring of the implementation of the regulation;

- the quality of education and to prepare the personnel specified requirements specify acceptable compared to the range of educational services which put;

- education and its ultimate results of education to the level of knowledge of the recipient were enrolled in the direction of the direction of education and the evaluation procedure and procedures from time to time, as well as educational activities compared to the control over the quality of improvement of the regulatory framework defining who put the relevant requirements;

- provided by pedagogical and information technologies of the educational process, to control the level of education, secondary scholarship recipient and graduate of the norms and institutions that put the revision of the qualification requirements;

- unbiased to evaluate the quality of the system of education and training, accreditation and certification of educational institutions revision of the indicator used in determining the quality of education;

- current state of the education standards in relation to the quality of education and training and qualification requirements in accordance with the requirements of international members on a permanent basis for improvement, go to ensure compliance;

- personnel control the quality of their preparation and knowledge focused on issues and objective evaluation of the system to the organization.

The important areas of this issue, raising the quality of education and the conditions of the scientific and theoretical basis of teachers, psychologist, philosopher, lawyer and siyosatshunos should be a critical analysis by scientists. First of all, as the subject of pedagogical sciences scientific research konseptual interpretation will require the following issues:

- education quality monitoring, the monitoring model of the concept, principles and its components;

- monitoring education quality model of the object, the subject, frequency, automated, electronic information system, effective forms and methods;

- education quality monitoring and modeling to go the scientific-theoretical basis;

- principles of the system of indicators of the quality of education, parameters, indicators of scientific-theoretical, methodological basis;

- education quality monitoring in the realization of didactic principles;

- a mechanism for monitoring the quality of education in the realization of the mutual influence of the factors that affect the quality of education and others.

Monitoring the quality of education pedagogy of methodological research on the basis of a complex character because he has his reason, sociology, psychology is based on the theory of science.

Collaboration between general education system in monitoring the implementation of several of the quality of education, pedagogical, psychological and social aspects of the concept was formed from an integral to a certain extent independent from affiliated: the quality of education, monitoring, and like the concept of the model.

The quality of education: secondary education institutions in our republic the educational process in the field of education quality reforms and priorities, as the ultimate result of all oshiritayotgan done is come in permanent control. Since the early days of independence by first president of the republic of uzbekistan, radical reform of the content of education, the quality of these personnel carried out in the republic of ready for the deep economic and social requirements, as well as education, science, engineering and technology world in order to ensure compliance with the advanced level of development of the main ideas put forward as "one of harmoniously developed generation, the foundation of the development of uzbekistan", as recorded etilib, "our children than we are strong, educated, wise, and of course must be happy" the fact that the president of the republic of uzbekistan Sh.M.Assign July 27, 2017. in "specialists with higher education in increasing the quality of participation and the preparation of further expansion of the network of sectors of the economy choratadbirlar" on pp-3151-dated Respublika education in pre-school institutions, primary music, fine arts, foreign languages, education, labor, physical education and other sciences on the areas of higher education for the training of teachers to meet the needs highly qualified teachers of educational institutions in regional and rural areas and prepare them to provide further improvement of the system in place in order to improve the quality of education through the organization from the academic year 2017/2018 secondary institutions on the organization of pedagogical aspects in the correspondence department special on August 9 2017 in "general correspondence pedagogical direction is the organization of special education institutions" on pp-3183son, 2017. September 26 "general education institutions targeted to improve the training of candidates for admission to the" pp-3290-through the practice of the resolution are introduced.

In pedagogical science "quality of education" concept, a number of interpretation, there is the interpretation. Definition of the concept of the quality of education and the education system to the development of visions, respectively, developing, improving and let go.

The origin of the concept of the quality of education in terms of the quality of education dealt with the history of the ancient period zvonnikov v. i. is being used in exactly the same which means it was noted that the applicant is described. In Particular, Martinenko V. Maslova, D. M. D. L. Sh.Matros v. n. Efremova n. f. Pugach own research and s "quality of education" the first of the initial period of development of the concept of the ancient world, which are available in the state darwin stems, I had the idea that.

"Quality" the concept of Aristotle see confirmation of existence vary as described. In his opinion because we are not qualitatively the same as with any other subject-specific properties. The concept of quality of a certain condition, the different aspects of the asset, the

subject-specific features, the location coordinates of the object consists of developing or moving on

Thoughts on this issue should be how the process of education philosophers of that period and the results, look at that identifies. Philosophers and scientists of the ancient world, in the opinion of the result of education and training should be put forward the idea that the perfection of the most effective man is located. Gerakl o'rgatmaydi to know more information and intelligence to be noted that Confucius to be the highest level of education the purpose of a person's moral character and virtues, rituals, traditions know, born and grown up in respect to the ground near the man himself is fond of, and be loved in it was noted that

Approaches to the eighteenth century came a radical change in the quality of education. In this period the concept of the improvement of education and knowledge, the defining factor is the quality of experience and scientific achievements of theoretical science began.

Robert ouen's "society of human character, or to find content on the experience explain new look called" the character of the people in the game will find it assumes that content in the conditions of the surrounding social environment. In his opinion, the actions of the people standing in the social environment they live depends on the situation. People-not even their character himself is not created and can never create it. You environment and culture changed, who put forward the idea that any character found in the content can explain.

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